

Determining Digital Financial Literacy Level of Social Generations in Muscat

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Abstract: This research intended to investigate the association between age and the digital financial literacy level and also its association with the financial decision-making attitude of individuals. A structured questionnaire was circulated among 250 Omani and foreign employees living in Muscat city, from February to March 2024. The primary data collected was analyzed by using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 software. The study uses Percentage analysis, Karl Pearson's correlation, Chi-square analysis, and One-way analysis of variance. The findings of the study demonstrated new insights into the relationship between the independent and dependent variables.

Index Terms: Digital financial literacy, Financial decision-making attitude, Social generations, Millennials, Generation Z.

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Rationale:

Nowadays, financial transactions are done online. For this purpose, individuals are expected to be aware of digital money management practices. Understanding online money management techniques is essential in today's digital world. Being capable of handling mobile applications and engaging in online banking for financial transfers are instances of possessing digital financial literacy. It has been found that digital financial knowledge directly impacts the financial attitude of people. A well-educated population with sound knowledge of digital finance can save more, invest properly, and improve their financial condition (Choung, 2023). The financial literacy level of people depends on various personal and behavioral factors. Studies have found that age level and knowledge level are closely associated as older age individuals possess better knowledge about savings and spending. Therefore, they usually take better decisions (Heneger & Cude, 2016). The young generation which is well acquainted with the modern technologies has an edge over usage of digital financial tools than the older generations (Dzokoto et. al., 2020). Hence it is imperative to establish the association between age and financial literacy and the financial attitude.

1.2 Objectives

The objectives of this research were as under:

- To determine the digital financial literacy level of the respondents across the social generations.
- To examine if the generational age of the participants is associated with their digital financial literacy level.
- To study if the generational age of the participants is associated with financial decision-making attitude.

II. PREVIOUS STUDIES AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Literature Review

The age and education level of 420 Indonesians belonging to generation Z were found to have a close association with the digital financial literacy. But gender and income were not the influencing factors of digital financial literacy (Muthia et.al., 2023). Choung et al. (2023) explored the relationship between the digital financial literacy and financial well-being of individuals in the age group of 25 to 59 years. The online poll was conducted in an anonymous manner, and demographic data was summarized using descriptive statistics. The Consumer Financial Protection Bureau's financial well-being scale and linear regression models were utilized. The study indicated that digital finance may increase financially excluded households' financial inclusion and reduce their poverty levels. Financial resilience is linked to digital and financial literacy, as well as risk management and sensible saving. Improving digital finance could increase the accessibility of mobile money and promote responsible spending.

Jennifer and Widoatmodjo (2023) explored how technological advances, financial education, and economic comprehension affected the money management practices of 150 young people in the age range of 18 to 35 years in Jakarta chosen using non-probability purposive sampling technique. The information gathered suggests that financial

technology, financial literacy, and financial education have a major positive influence on young people's financial management practices in Jakarta. Uddin and Mohammed Ahmar (2022) explored the effect of financial literacy on personal savings of 200 Omani individuals using the Logistic regression model. It was found that those who are financially knowledgeable are more likely to save money. Cupak et.al. (2022) examined how the level of financial literacy affects the investment behavior. of 5777 US households, selected from the Survey of Consumer Finances (SCF) as a source of secondary data. They analyzed the data using unconditional quantile regressions. It was discovered that higher financial literacy increases the probability of investing in risky assets. Peiris (2021) investigated the impact of financial literacy on savings behavior, considering the mediation role of the intention to save. The study focused on individuals with jobs in Western Sri Lanka, and data were collected from 206 out of 385 participants through online surveys. Structural equation modeling (SEM) was employed as the methodology. The findings revealed a positive influence of financial literacy on savings behavior, indicating that a strong understanding of the financial system encouraged better saving habits, particularly a heightened desire to save more money.

Bhutta et.al (2021) investigated the relationship between financial literacy and liquid savings among U.S. households. They took the data from SCF portal and used descriptive, regression and robustness checks. It was found that the higher degree of financial literacy had a positive effect on savings. Liu and Zhang (2021) examined the relationship between college students' financial literacy and risky credit behavior. A total of 539 Chinese college students participated in this study. The data for this study was gathered using an online survey. The sample for this investigation was selected by using simple random selection. For the data collection, a thousand questionnaires were developed. The interviews that were conducted in this study were analyzed using a five-point Likert scale. The results demonstrated that the financial literacy of these students had a significant influence on their risky credit behavior, with subjective financial literacy having a greater influence than objective financial literacy. Furthermore, risky credit behavior and financial literacy are more strongly correlated among college students who report significant levels of stress related to money concerns. A study conducted in 371 respondents in Ghana revealed that the youth are more digitally literate than the older generations (Dzokoto et. al., 2020).

2.2 Conceptual Framework

The literature review explains that the financial attitude of people is motivated by their financial awareness. The financial awareness as well as financial behavior of individuals varies according to the demographic features. Most of the literature confirm a positive relationship between age and the two variables. Therefore, the conceptual model has one independent variable and two dependent variables.

Figure 2.2: Conceptual Model of the Research

2.3 Research Hypotheses

- Null Hypothesis 1 (H_{01}): The digital financial literacy level of the participants does not depend on their age groups.
- Null hypothesis 2 (H_{02}): The financial decision-making attitude of the participants is not linked to the age groups.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design:

This is descriptive research paper using quantitative method to assess the effect of social generation on the digital financial literacy and financial decision-making attitude. A structured Google form questionnaire was used to collect data from 250 participants, selected by using non-probability snowball sampling technique. The research instrument was divided into three sections, comprised of close-ended multiple-choice questions as well as Likert scale type questions. The first section focused on demographic information, such as nationality, age, gender, education, marital status, income. The second section dived into the assessment of Digital Financial Literacy Level (Moore's Scale, 2003) and third section questioned the participants about their .

3.2 Research Sample

The sample size of 250 comprised of Omani citizens as well as expatriate workers who were in the age group of 19 to more than 60 years of age. They belonged to the working class were representation of both Government and private sector employees were found. Based on the social generations' theory (Mannheim, 1923), the sample was divided into four generations viz., Baby Boomers, Generation X, Generation Y (i.e., Millennials) and Generation Z.

3.3 Research Area and Period

The research was conducted within the capital city of Muscat. The primary data was collected during the months of February and March 2024.

IV. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Reliability and Validity

The data collected through google forms were analyzed with the help of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. Karl Pearson's correlation, regression analysis, one-way analysis of variance, Chi-square test and Sentiment analysis. The Cronbach's alpha was 0.767 which means that there was a reasonable level of consistency and reliability in the measurement of data. There were 26 items of questions with 250 valid and complete responses. The question items in the research instrument were interrelated and has measured the research concept fairly and consistently.

4.2 Determination of the level of Digital Financial Literacy

To determine the digital financial literacy level of the sample, three groups were set up based on the mean value of the digital financial literacy responses. The mean value was 3.88 as per the test statistics. The respondents who scored more than 3.88 were categorized as the group having high digital literacy level. The second group was comprised of the respondents who earned a score between 3 and 3.88. They were classified as having average digital financial literacy. The third consisted of respondents who scored less than 3. They are falling under the category of low digital financial literacy. The results are tabulated as under:

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Low	16	6.4	6.4
	Average	111	44.4	50.8
	High	123	49.2	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	

Source: Processed Data

The mean digital financial literacy score was 3.88. This point was taken as the central value in determining the digital financial literacy level. Group 1 represented individuals with low mean scores, ranging from 1 to 2.99, indicating lower proficiency, while Group 2 included those with mean value from 3 to 3.88, and Group 3 comprised of respondents with high scores which are having mean of 3.89 and higher, reflecting superior financial knowledge. A minority, 6.4% of the overall sample, demonstrated a low digital financial literacy level, as evidenced by strong disagreement with the survey questions, resulting in a mean ranging from 1 to 2.99. Furthermore, 44.4% of respondents displayed an average level of competency, indicating a neutral attitude towards the questions, with mean scores ranging from 3 to 3.88. In contrast, most respondents (49.2%) demonstrated a high level of digital financial literacy, as reflected by constant agreement with the literacy questions, resulting in mean scores of 3.89 or above. To find the number of respondents falling under the above groups according to the age category, a cross tab was generated, and the results are presented in Figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2: Digital Financial Literacy Level Assessment

Source: Processed Data

Figure 4.2 depicts the information about the distribution of digital financial literacy levels across the different generations that the participants belonged to, i.e., Generation Z, Millennials (also known as Generation Y), Generation X, and Baby Boomers. Among the Generation Z group, there were a total of 64 participants. The Millennials age group consisted of 104 participants. Generation X had 72 participants, while the Baby Boomers age group comprised 10 participants only. Within Generation Z individuals, 5 individuals have a Low digital financial literacy level, 23 have an Average digital financial literacy level, and 36 have a High digital financial literacy level. For Millennials, 5 individuals have a Low digital financial literacy level, 47 have an Average digital financial literacy level, and 52 have a High digital financial literacy level. In the Generation X group, 6 individuals have a Low digital financial literacy level, 36 have an Average digital financial literacy level, and 30 have a High digital financial literacy level. In the category Baby Boomers, no one belonged to the Low digital financial literacy level, whereas 5 participants had an Average digital financial literacy level, and 5 individuals with a High digital financial literacy level. Most of the respondents having average and high levels of digital financial literacy were from the Millennials group.

4.3 Hypothesis Testing 1

A chi-square analysis was run on the digital financial literacy level and the age groups cross tab, which produced the following output:

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	4.790 ^a	6	0.571
Likelihood Ratio	5.486	6	0.483
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.247	1	0.264
N of Valid Cases	250		

Source: Processed Data

The Pearson chi-square test used to investigate the association between the age groups and digital financial literacy levels showed a p-value of 0.571 which is higher than the significance level of 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis was accepted, and the alternative hypothesis was rejected. So, it was found that there was no association between the age of individuals and their digital financial literacy level among the sample participants.

4.4 Association between Age and Financial Decision-Making Attitude

To study the relationship between the age of the sample respondents and financial decision-making behavior, the following one-way analysis of variance test was conducted.

Mean Financial Decision-Making Attitude	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.019	3	0.340	0.938	0.423
Within Groups	89.077	246	0.362		
Total	90.096	249			

Source: Processed Data

The one-way ANOVA between age and financial decision-making attitude is displayed in Table 4.4. The df=249, the F value was 0.938 (p=0.423). The findings are statistically insignificant when the p-value is greater than 0.05. So, it was found that there was no association between the age of the participants and their digital financial literacy level among the sample participants.

4.5 Hypothesis Testing 2

The results of Table 4.4 were used to investigate the association between the social generation groups and financial decision-making attitude. At 95% confidence level, the association was not statistically significant. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted, and the alternative hypothesis is rejected. So, there was no association between the age of the participants and their financial decision-making attitude.

V. DISCUSSION ON FINDINGS

The participants belonging to the Millennial generation (i.e., Generation Y) had high level of digital financial literacy, followed by Generation Z and X. There was no association between an individual's age and level of digital financial literacy as well as their financial decision-making attitude. Despite the digital gap between the generations, the result found no significant association between the age of the participants and digital financial literacy levels. The findings suggest that participants' age does not have a considerable impact on shaping their financial behavior. The study also found that other factors take precedence over age in determining digital financial literacy and financial behavior. This may be because the sample had only ten participants from the older social generation group. Most of the working class in Muscat city belonged to the Generation Y (i.e., millennials) category. The study also contradicted the generation

perspective research which mentioned that the younger generation is more digitally literate than the older generations (Dzokoto et. al., 2020).

VI. CONCLUSION

The increasing use of digital money management tools for managing money highlights the significance of grasping digital financial literacy. This literacy level plays a role in shaping individuals' financial choices and outcomes enabling them to assess and manage financial risks while making decisions that match their personal goals. Through this research, it has been discovered that age or the category of social generation of an individual is not a sole determining factor of financial literacy, which contradicts the earlier research which mentioned that the relationship between the age and the level of financial literacy (Nguyen, 2022). This study suggests that it is important for the government to place its efforts towards increasing the digital financial literacy level of people by implementing various financial education programs. As our research present a counter argument to what has been discovered in the past studies regarding the association between the age and digital financial literacy level.

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